

Robustness of Divergence Time Estimation Despite Gene Tree Error: A Case Study of Fireflies (Coleoptera: Lampyridae)

Supplementary Material

R.H. Divergence Time Estimation Despite Gene Tree Error

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1 S1 Genera, Tribes and Sub-families

Table S1: Genera, Tribes and Sub-families used to assess gene-tree error and clade ages.

Name	Species
Psilocladus	Psilocladus sigillatus, Psilocladus sp 1, Psilocladus sp 2
Vesta	Vesta impressicollis, Vesta saturnalis, Vesta sp
Amydetinae	Amydetes fastigiata, Cladodes illigeri, Ethra axillaris, Memoan ciceroi, Psilocladus sigillatus, Psilocladus sp 1, Psilocladus sp 2, Vesta impressicollis, Vesta saturnalis, Vesta sp
Lamprohizinae	Lamprohiza splendidula, Phausis reticulata
Aspisoma	Aspisoma sp, Aspisoma sticticum
Pyractomena	Pyractomena borealis, Pyractonema sp 1, Pyractonema sp 2
Cratomorphini	Aspisoma sp, Aspisoma sticticum, Cratomorphus sp, Pyractomena borealis, Pyractonema sp 1, Pyractonema sp 2
Lamprocera	Lamprocera sp 1, Lamprocera sp 2, Lamprocera sp 3, Lamprocera sp 4
Lamprocerini	Lamprocera sp 1, Lamprocera sp 2, Lamprocera sp 3, Lamprocera sp 4, Lucio blattinum, Lychnacris sp, Tenaspis angularis
Diaphanes	Diaphanes pectinealis, Diaphanes sp 1, Diaphanes sp 2, Diaphanes sp 3, Diaphanes sp 4
Lampyrini	Diaphanes pectinealis, Diaphanes sp 1, Diaphanes sp 2, Diaphanes sp 3, Diaphanes sp 4, Lampyris noctiluca, Microphotus sp, Petalacmis sp, Pleotomodes needhami, Pyrocoelia pygidialis
Ellychnia	Ellychnia corrusca, Ellychnia sp
Photinus	Photinus sp 1, Photinus sp 2, Photinus floridanus, Photinus macdermotti 1, Photinus stellaris, Photinus ardens, Photinus carolinus, Photinus pyralis, Ellychnia sp, Ellychnia corrusca, Photinus macdermotti 2, Photinus granulatus, Photinus australis, Photinus brimleyi
Pyropyga	Pyropyga decipiens, Pyropyga nigricans
Photinini	Photinini sp , Ellychnia corrusca, Ellychnia sp, Heterophotinus sp, Lamprigera yunnana, Photinus sp 1, Photinus sp 2, Photinus floridanus, Photinus macdermotti 2, Photinus stellaris, Photinus ardens, Photinus carolinus, Photinus pyralis, Ellychnia sp, Ellychnia corrusca, Photinus macdermotti 1, Photinus granulatus, Photinus australis, Photinus brimleyi, Pyropyga decipiens, Pyropyga nigricans
Phosphaenini	Lucidota atra, Phosphaenopterus sp
Lampyrinae	Aspisoma sp, Aspisoma sticticum, Cratomorphus sp, Pyractomena borealis, Pyractonema sp 1, Pyractonema sp 2, Lamprocera sp 1, Lamprocera sp 2, Lamprocera sp 3, Lamprocera sp 4, Lucio blattinum, Lychnacris sp, Tenaspis angularis, Diaphanes pectinealis, Diaphanes sp 1, Diaphanes sp 2, Diaphanes sp 3, Diaphanes sp 4, Lampyris noctiluca, Microphotus sp, Petalacmis sp, Pleotomodes needhami, Pyrocoelia pygidialis, Photinini sp , Ellychnia corrusca, Ellychnia sp, Heterophotinus sp, Lamprigera yunnana, Photinus sp 1, Photinus sp 2, Photinus floridanus, Photinus macdermotti 2, Photinus stellaris, Photinus ardens, Photinus carolinus, Photinus pyralis, Ellychnia sp, Ellychnia corrusca, Photinus macdermotti 1, Photinus granulatus, Photinus australis, Photinus brimleyi, Pyropyga decipiens, Pyropyga nigricans, Lucidota atra, Phosphaenopterus sp
Australoluciola	Australoluciola nigra, Australoluciola sp
Curtos	Curtos sp, Curtos bilineatus, Curtos obsuricolor
Luciola	Luciola sp 1, Luciola sp 2
Luciolini	Abscondita cerata, Asymmetrica circumdata, Atyphella flammulans, Australoluciola sp, Australoluciola nigra, Curtos sp, Curtos bilineatus, Curtos obsuricolor, Emeia pseudosauteri, Lloydiella uberia, Luciola sp 1, Luciola sp 2, Pteroptyx sp, Pygoluciola qinqyu, Trisinuata sp
Luciolinae	Luciolinae sp, Luciolinae nr Luciola 1, Luciolinae nr Luciola 2, Luciolinae nr Luciola 3, Luciolinae nr Luciola 4, Abscondita cerata, Asymmetrica circumdata, Atyphella flammulans, Australoluciola sp, Australoluciola nigra, Curtos sp, Curtos bilineatus, Curtos obsuricolor, Emeia pseudosauteri, Lloydiella uberia, Luciola sp 1, Luciola sp 2, Pteroptyx sp, Pygoluciola qinqyu, Trisinuata sp
Ototretinae	Drilaster sp, Stenocladus shirakii
Bicellonycha	Bicellonycha sp 1, Bicellonycha sp 2
Photuris	Photuris congener, Photuris divisia, Photuris frontalis, Photuris quadrifulgens
Photurinae	Bicellonycha sp 1, Bicellonycha sp 2, Photuris congener, Photuris divisia, Photuris frontalis, Photuris quadrifulgens, Pyrogaster sp

2 S2 Fossil Calibrations

Table S2: Fossils and calibration constraints for the time-calibrated divergence time analysis.

Fossil taxon	Max age (MA)	Min age (Ma)	Reference	Monophyletic clade constraint
† <i>Lampyris orciluca</i>	12.7	11.608	Heer (1865)	† <i>Lampyris orciluca</i> , <i>Lampyris noctiluca</i>
† <i>Lamprohiza fossilis</i>	28.4	23.03	Kazantsev (2012)	† <i>Lamprohiza fossilis</i> , <i>Lamprohiza splendidula</i>
† <i>Lucidota prima</i>	37.2	33.9	Wickham (1912)	† <i>Lucidota prima</i> , <i>Lucidota atra</i>
† <i>Photinus kazantsevi</i>	37.2	33.9	Alekseev (2019)	† <i>Photinus kazantsevi</i> , <i>Photinus sp 1</i> , <i>Photinus sp 2</i> , <i>Photinus floridanus</i> , <i>Photinus macdermotti 2</i> , <i>Photinus stellaris</i> , <i>Photinus ardens</i> , <i>Photinus carolinus</i> , <i>Photinus pyralis</i> , <i>Ellychnia sp</i> , <i>Ellychnia corrusca</i> , <i>Photinus macdermotti 1</i> , <i>Photinus granulatus</i> , <i>Photinus australis</i> , <i>Photinus brimleyi</i>

3 Estimating a dated phylogeny of most insect clades is extremely challenging because of the lack of
 4 appropriate fossils for node calibrations. We used four fossil taxa belonging to different genera within
 5 Lampyridae (Table S2). We used †*Lampyris orciluca* (Heer 1865) which belongs to the genus *Lampyris*, and
 6 †*Lucidota prima* (Wickham 1912) which belongs to the genus *Lucidota*. Additionally we used †*Lamprohiza*
 7 *fossilis* (Kazantsev 2012) and placed it belonging to the genus *Lamprohiza*, although †*Lamprohiza fossilis*
 8 was previously named †*Phausis fossilis* (Beier 1952). Since *Phausis* and *Lamprohiza* are the only two genera
 9 in the subfamily Lamprohizinae, our calibration is equivalent to a minimum age of Lamprohizinae because
 10 the split *Phausis* – *Lamprohiza* must have occurred before the age of †*Lamprohiza fossilis*.

11 We included the recently published fossil for the *Photinus* clade; †*Photinus kazantsevi* found in Baltic
 12 amber and dated to the Upper or Mid-Eocene (33.9 to 47.8 Ma, Alekseev 2019). However, the taxonomic
 13 placement of this fossil specimen is unknown, *i.e.*, whether this fossil represent a stem or crown fossil. To
 14 explore the sensitivity of our fossil calibrations and divergence time analyses, we performed each divergence
 15 time analyses for the four data subsets twice; once including †*Photinus kazantsevi* and enforcing *Photinus* to
 16 be monophyletic and the other time excluding †*Photinus kazantsevi*. This sensitivity analysis provides both
 17 insights into the robustness of the divergence time analysis when a fossil is excluded (Near and Sanderson
 18 2004; Saladin et al. 2017) and the placement of †*Photinus kazantsevi*.

19 We omitted using the fossil †*Electrotreta rasnitsyni* because our preliminary analyses showed that *Dri-*
 20 *laster sp* and *Stenocladus shirakii* were not recovered as sister species (see also Martin et al. 2019). We did
 21 not want to enforce the sister relationship between *Drilaster sp* and *Stenocladus shirakii* because this could
 22 bias the phylogeny inference. Similarly, we omitted the use of the fossil †*Protoluciola albertalleni* (Kazantsev
 23 2015) because the phylogenetic relationship of *Luciola* are under continuous revision and thus the place-
 24 ment of the fossil is very uncertain. Nevertheless, since †*Protoluciola albertalleni* is a fossil Luciolinae from
 25 Burmite amber (~99 million year old), it provides a minimum age for Lampyridae of at least 99 Ma.

Figure S1: Completeness of the AHE dataset of [Martin et al. \(2019\)](#). We computed the percentage of sites missing per sequence. Black cells depict complete sequences and white cells depict entirely missing sequence. The gray shades depict the percentage in between. Each row represents one of the 436 AHE loci and each column represent one taxon. We highlighted the *Photinus* (P) and *Ellychnia* (E) species using tick marks.

Figure S2: Overlap of the AHE data subsets. We selected four data subsets based on (a) loci with on average 95% completeness (high coverage), (b) loci with a high posterior probability of *Photinus + Ellychnia* being monophyletic (high PP), (c) loci with low variance in GC content, and (d) root to tip branch length variation and clade support (gene shopping). Shows the overlap between data subsets. Despite there being some overlap between the data subsets, the majority of loci are private to each subset.

27 **S4 Simulated alignments**

Figure S3: Example locus for the simulations. The top alignment shows the empirical data. The second row shows the simulated dataset with complete sequences and homogeneous (*i.e.*, independent and identically distributed, IID) highly variable sites. The third row shows the simulated dataset with missing sequences and homogeneous highly variable sites. The fourth row shows the simulated dataset with complete sequences and systematically distributed (*i.e.*, akin to the empirical AHE dataset) highly variable sites. The fifth row shows the simulated dataset with missing sequences and systematically distributed highly variable sites.

28 **S5 Data Summary**

Figure S4: Summary statistics obtained for the AHE dataset of Martin et al. (2019). We computed the frequencies of summary statistics for the 436 AHE loci. Specifically, we computed the number of variable sites, number of invariant sites, minimum pairwise distance, maximum pairwise distance, minimum GC content, maximum GC content, mean GC content and variance of GC content.

29 We obtained a minimum of 218 variables sites and a maximum of 2,071 variable sites with a mean of 696
 30 variable sites (Figure S4). Similarly, we obtained a minimum of 23 invariable sites, a maximum of 1067
 31 invariable sites and a mean of 225 invariable sites. We used the number of variable sites as a proxy for how
 32 informative a locus is (Townsend 2007). Overall, the distribution of the number of variable sites appeared
 33 unimodal without extremely low outliers. Thus, we did not see any indication that specific loci should be
 34 particularly poor for phylogenetic inference.

35 The minimum and maximum pairwise distance showed interesting patterns. The majority of loci had a
 36 minimum pairwise distance of zero (Figure S4), which means that the alignments contained two sequences
 37 without substitutions among them. Hence, there is no phylogenetic signal to distinguish between the se-
 38 quences. In itself, this low pairwise distance does not imply a problem for phylogenetic inference because
 39 the two taxa will be placed as sister taxa. However, this distribution could indicate that there are several
 40 taxa that cannot be resolved.

41 The maximum pairwise distance showed a skewed distribution with some larger outliers. This could
 42 indeed be problematic. First, the high maximum pairwise distance will most likely lead to long branches in
 43 the phylogeny. Second, the high distance could occur due to non-homologous sequences. The sequences, for
 44 example, could be contaminated, mis-aligned and/or represent paralogs.

45 The distribution of GC content showed some slightly multi-modal and skewed mean GC content and
 46 variance in GC content (Figure S4). The mode with lower mean GC content and higher variance in GC

47 content could represent loci which are problematic for phylogenetic inference.

S6 Posterior probabilities of single loci

Figure S5: Posterior probability of all 26 subfamilies, tribes and genera being monophyletic per AHE locus. For each AHE locus, we computed the posterior probability that the clade is monophyletic. A histogram with most loci having a high posterior probability (*e.g.*, *Vesta*) depicts strong support by the majority of AHE loci. Conversely, a histogram with most loci having a low posterior probability (*e.g.*, *Photinus*) depicts strong support against monophyly by the majority of AHE loci. Four of the six subfamilies were not monophyletic. Only Lamprohizinae was found to be monophyletic for the majority of loci and Ototretinae was ambiguously supported. None of the six tribes was found to be monophyletic. Several genera are strongly rejected (*Pyractomena*, *Diaphanes*, *Photinus*, *Luciola* and *Curtos*).

S7 Assessing potential correlations to posterior probabilities

Figure S6: Comparison between phylogenetic accuracy (*i.e.*, posterior probability of the clade *Photinus+Ellychnia* being monophyletic), model adequacy (*i.e.*, posterior predictive p-values) and data summary statistics obtained for the AHE dataset of [Martin et al. \(2019\)](#). In green we show the comparison between data summary statistics (x-axis) and the posterior probability of *Photinus* being monophyletic (y-axis). In blue we show the comparison between posterior predictive p-values (x-axis) and the posterior probability of *Photinus* being monophyletic (y-axis). In red we show the comparison between data summary statistics (x-axis) and posterior predictive p-values (y-axis). The dashed lines represent smoothed spline function of the corresponding comparisons. Note that for the variance of GC content we could not plot a predictor function because all posterior predictive p-values are 0.0. We observe that there is no correlation between model adequacy (posterior predictive p-values) and the posterior probability of *Photinus+Ellychnia* being monophyletic (blue line). Interestingly, we observe some correlation between data summary statistics and model adequacy (red line). For each AHE locus, we computed the posterior probability that the clade *Photinus + Ellychnia* is monophyletic. We show each comparison separately in [Figure S8](#), [S7](#) and [S10](#).

50 S7.1 Correlation between missing data and posterior support

51 Given the poor support on higher taxonomic levels, and the ambiguous support for some of the named clades
52 (Figure S5), we investigated whether there is a correlation between missing data and phylogenetic accuracy.
53 Here, we associate phylogenetic accuracy with the ability to recover monophyly of an established clade.
54 Specifically, we used the posterior probability of *Photinus+Ellychnia* being monophyletic. We focus here on
55 *Photinus+Ellychnia* because it is a well studied genus whose monophyly is not debated (Stanger-Hall et al.
56 2007; Lower et al. 2017; Martin et al. 2019) although we observed rather ambiguous support (Figure S5).
57 The same investigation for all named clades is shown in Figure S8.

Figure S7: Comparison of posterior probability of the clade *Photinus* being monophyletic to sequence coverage and other summary statistics obtained for the AHE dataset of Martin et al. (2019). For each AHE locus, we computed the posterior probability that the clade *Photinus* is monophyletic. We computed the percentage of missing sites (coverage) as well as the summary statistics for the 436 AHE loci. Specifically, we computed the number of multinomial likelihood, variable sites, number of invariant sites, minimum pairwise distance, maximum pairwise distance, minimum GC content, maximum GC content, mean GC content and variance of GC content.

58 We observed that there is no correlation between sequence coverage and the posterior probability of
59 *Photinus+Ellychnia* being monophyletic (Figures S7 and S8). This results is actually expected because we
60 removed taxa which had 50% or more sites in the sequence missing. The overall sequence coverage instead
61 represents the completeness of the entire alignment and therefore loci with higher average sequence coverage
62 are loci that contain more taxa after pruning. The same trend and correlation between sequence coverage and
63 phylogenetic accuracy can be seen for all other tested clades (Figure S8). Thus, our pruning of incomplete
64 sequences from the alignment makes filtering loci based on overall sequence coverage futile.

65 S7.2 Correlation between summary statistics of the data and posterior support

66 Next to the sequence completeness of a loci, other summary statistics of the data could provide good indica-
67 tors about the quality and usefulness of a locus (phylogenetic accuracy). Again, we used the ability to recover
68 monophyly of the clade *Photinus+Ellychnia* as a predictor for phylogenetic accuracy. We compared several
69 summary statistics to the posterior probability of *Photinus+Ellychnia* being monophyletic (Figure S6, green

70 dots and green dashed line, and Figure S7). Instead of seeing clear trends (*i.e.*, monotonously increasing
71 or decreasing correlations), we observed unimodal correlation (*e.g.*, for the number of invariant sites). That
72 means that outlier loci with extreme values for the summary statistics produce lower phylogenetic accuracy
73 (*e.g.*, number of invariant sites, minimum GC content and maximum GC content). Only for the minimum
74 pairwise distance and the variance in GC content did we observe a positive correlation (and negative corre-
75 lation, respectively) with phylogenetic accuracy. A negative correlation between the variance in GC content
76 and phylogenetic accuracy is expected because a low variance in GC content corresponds to more homo-
77 geneous substitution processes which are easier to model and produce less biased phylogenetic estimates
78 (Foster 2004). Most importantly, the single loci (Figure S6, green dots) show large variations and the overall
79 trends computed by the average might mislead conclusions.

Figure S8: Posterior probability of a clade being monophyletic per AHE locus versus the percentage of missing sites. For each AHE locus, we computed the posterior probability that a given clade is monophyletic. We then compared the posterior probability of the clade being monophyletic to the percentage of missing sites for the locus. Each gray dot represents a single locus. The loci are plotted as opaque to better show clusters. The black dots connected by the black dashed line show the rolling average of 20 loci.

80 **S8 Model Adequacy**

81 **S8.1 Posterior Predictive P-values**

Figure S9: Posterior predictive p-values for each AHE locus. For each AHE locus, we simulated from the posterior predictive distribution and computed the posterior predictive p-value for various summary statistics. Specifically, we computed the number of variable sites, number of invariant sites, minimum pairwise distance, maximum pairwise distance, minimum GC content, maximum GC content, mean GC content and variance of GC content. Interestingly, most posterior predictive p-values show clear model violations, which could induce biased phylogenetic tree estimates. Surprisingly, even simple summary statistics that are usually modeled adequately, such as number of variable sites and number of invariant sites, are strongly violated.

82 S8.2 Correlation between posterior predictive p-values and posterior support

83 We observed no clear correlation between the posterior predictive p-values and the gene tree estimation
84 accuracy (when assuming monophyly of *Photinus+Ellychnia* as a proxy for gene tree accuracy, Figure S6
85 blue dots and dashed blue line). However, we observed a negative correlation between several summary
86 statistics and posterior predictive p-values (Figure S6 red dots and dashed red line). This indicates that
87 large summary statistics represent loci which are likely to be outliers which we cannot model adequately.
88 For example, a high minimum or maximum pairwise distance could be alignment errors and removing these
89 loci could improve phylogenetic inference.

Figure S10: Comparison of posterior probability of the clade *Photinus* being monophyletic to posterior predictive p-values. The dashed black line shows a rolling average. There does not seem to be a trend or correlation between posterior predictive p-value and posterior probability of the clade *Photinus*. Thus, none of the chosen summary statistics is a good indicator of gene tree error (assuming the posterior probability of *Photinus* being monophyletic as a proxy for gene tree accuracy).

90 **S8.3 Correlation between posterior predictive p-values and data summary statis-**
 91 **tics**

Figure S11: Correlation between summary statistics and posterior predictive p-values. The dashed black line shows a rolling average and the solid green line shows the regression line. There is a negative correlation between all summary statistics and the posterior predictive p-values. Model adequacy is thus improved when considering loci with lower values for these nine summary statistics.

92 **S9 Simulation Study**

93 **S9.1 Impact of missing data on summary statistics**

Figure S12: Summary statistics of the empirical AHE datasets and simulated datasets. The bottom row shows the summary statistics computed for the empirical dataset of [Martin et al. \(2019\)](#). The simulated datasets show similar distributions to the empirical dataset only if missing sequences were considered. The second row shows the summary statistics computed for the simulated dataset with complete sequences and homogeneous (*i.e.*, independent and identically distributed, IID) highly variable sites. The third row shows the summary statistics computed for the simulated dataset with missing sequences and homogeneous highly variable sites. The fourth row shows the summary statistics computed for the simulated dataset with complete sequences and systematically distributed (*i.e.*, akin to the empirical AHE dataset) highly variable sites. The bottom row shows the summary statistics computed for the simulated dataset with missing sequences and systematically distributed highly variable sites. The distribution of highly variables versus conserved sites had little to no impact on the summary statistics.

S10 Gene tree discordance

Figure S13: Gene tree discordance measured using the normalized Robinson-Foulds (RF) distance between several reference trees and the single gene trees for all three simulation settings. The top row shows the simulations for low population sizes (100,000), the middle row for intermediate population sizes (1,000,000) and the bottom row for large population sizes (10,000,000). As reference trees, we used the the maximum a posterior (MAP) phylogeny using the four different data subsets (high coverage, low variance in GC content, high posterior probability of *Photinus+Ellychnia* being monophyletic, and gene shopping). The left panel shows the frequency of the RF-distance for the empirical dataset of [Martin et al. \(2019\)](#). The second panel shows the RF-distance for the simulated dataset with complete sequences and homogeneous (*i.e.*, independent and identically distributed, IID) highly variables sites. The third panel shows the RF-distance for the simulated dataset with complete sequences and systematically distributed (*i.e.*, akin to the empirical AHE dataset) highly variables sites. The right panel shows the RF-distance for the simulated dataset with missing sequences and systematically distributed highly variable sites. Neither of our simulation conditions show a strongly negative impact on gene tree discordance (each column shows the same pattern).

95 S11 Posterior probabilities of given clades using single gene trees
 96 and the simulated data

Figure S14: Posterior probabilities for the clades using the simulated dataset with complete sequences and homogeneous (*i.e.*, independent and identically distributed, IID) highly variable sites. The posterior probabilities without missing data, *i.e.*, complete sequences, show strong support for the correct clades.

Figure S15: Posterior probabilities for the clades using the simulated dataset with missing sequences and homogeneous (*i.e.*, independent and identically distributed, IID) highly variable sites. The posterior probabilities with missing data has reduced support for the correct clade. Specifically, the *Photinus* clade has significantly reduced support, whereas *Phosphaenini* and *Australoluciola* have spuriously inflated support.

Figure S16: Posterior probabilities for the clades using the simulated dataset with complete sequences and systematically distributed highly variable sites. The posterior probabilities without missing data, *i.e.*, complete sequences, show strong support for the correct clades.

Figure S17: Posterior probabilities for the clades using the simulated dataset with missing sequences and systematically distributed highly variable sites. The posterior probabilities with missing data has reduced support for the correct clade. Specifically, the *Photinus* clade has significantly reduced support, whereas Phosphaenini and *Australoluciola* have spuriously inflated support.

S12 Simulation Study of Gene Tree Discordance with Alignment Errors

To explore the impact of sequence and alignment errors, we simulated ten sets of 15 loci along the “true” Lampyridae phylogeny. As in our other simulation study, we used empirically informed substitution model parameters. Specifically, we assumed a GTR+ Γ model with base frequencies $\pi = \{0.31, 0.17, 0.19, 0.33\}$, substitution rates $\epsilon = \{0.087, 0.295, 0.08, 0.09, 0.38, 0.068\}$ and site rate categories $r = \{0.039, 0.271, 0.841, 2.849\}$. The branch rates were drawn from a uncorrelated lognormal relaxed clock model with mean 1.836×10^{-3} (in million years, see Keightley et al. (2015)) and standard deviation of 0.58, thus specifying that 95% of the distribution spans one order of magnitude. Then, we simulated sequence data using RevBayes under an error model with 0.1, 1 and 10% error probability. That is, for each nucleotide at the tips of the phylogeny, we decided with the given probability if the nucleotide will be replaced with one of the three “incorrect” nucleotides.

First, we used the three sets of 150 alignments to estimate gene trees based on our standard pipeline. The observed gene tree estimation error is lower compared to the empirical dataset even if 10% of nucleotides were randomly replaced (Figure S18). Second, we concatenated the 15 loci of each of the 10 simulation replicates to infer divergence times using the same model and analysis settings including calibrations from our empirical analysis. Interestingly, divergence times were strongly biased with increased sequence error (Figure S19)

Figure S18: Gene tree discordance measured using the normalized Robinson-Foulds (RF) distance for alignments with errors. The left dataset shows the gene trees estimated from the 436 empirical loci. The other three dataset are 150 simulated loci each using the Lampyridae phylogeny (reference for RF distances) with different error probabilities for randomly replacing nucleotides: 0.1, 1 and 10%.

Figure S19: Crown age estimates of the named clades from Table S1. Each plot shows the posterior distribution of the crown age of a different clade for the three error probabilities in the simulations: 0.1, 1 and 10%. The red dashed line shows the true age of the clade used in the simulation.

115 **S13 Simulation Study of Divergence Time Estimation with Gene** 116 **Tree Discordance**

117 To explore the impact of gene tree discordance on using a concatenated alignment for divergence time estima-
118 tion, we performed a simulation with four settings to simulate gene trees. First, we used the estimated gene
119 trees selected using the `gene shopping` (Smith et al. 2018) approach. Second, we simulated gene trees under
120 a multispecies coalescent model with the “true” Lampyridae phylogeny as species tree and an assumed effec-
121 tive population size of 500k. Third, we randomly picked 15 gene trees from the empirical Lampyridae dataset.
122 Fourth, we used the species tree as the gene trees (i.e., no gene tree discordance). For each of these settings,
123 we constructed ten replicates of 15 gene trees. Then, we simulated sequence data under a GTR+ Γ model
124 with base frequencies $\pi = \{0.31, 0.17, 0.19, 0.33\}$, substitution rates $\epsilon = \{0.087, 0.295, 0.08, 0.09, 0.38, 0.068\}$
125 and site rate categories $r = \{0.039, 0.271, 0.841, 2.849\}$. Finally, all 15 simulated loci were concatenated,
126 resulting in 4×10 simulated datasets. We analyzed each of these 40 datasets under the same pipeline as
127 used for the empirical analysis for estimating divergence times. A summary of the resulting divergence time
128 estimates is shown in Figure S20. We observed an increased uncertainty in divergence time estimates with
129 increased levels for gene tree discordance.

Figure S20: Crown age estimates of several representative named clades from Table S1. Each plot shows the posterior distribution of the crown age of a different clade for the four different settings to simulate gene tree discordance: (i) using the 15 gene trees obtained from the *gene shopping* (Smith et al. 2018) approach, (ii) simulating under the multispecies coalescent model, (iii) using randomly chosen empirical gene trees, and (iv) using the “true” species tree for the gene trees. For each setting, ten replicates of 15 simulated loci were concatenated and used for divergence time estimation. The red dashed line shows the true age of the clade used in the simulation.

S14 Lampyridae phylogeny and divergence times

S14.1 Topology of Lampyridae

The estimated topology of the dated Lampyrid tree is largely congruent with that presented in [Martin et al. \(2019\)](#), which was generated with the same AHE dataset without fossil calibration. However, there are some minor differences between the two trees, distributed throughout the phylogeny (Figure 4, Supplementary Table S3). While the core topology of our dated tree supports the recent higher-level classification ([Martin et al. 2019](#)), these minor topological differences have the potential to influence evolutionary analyses, thus highlighting the need for expanded taxonomic and phylogenomic investigations of fireflies, as well as development of robust phylogenomic methods in general.

Table S3: Differences between [Martin et al. \(2019\)](#) phylogeny and the phylogeny estimated in this study.

Clade	Martin et al. (2019)	This study
Higher level (e.g., between tribes and subfamilies)		
Psilocladinae	Sister to Photurinae + Amydetinae + Vesta	Sister to Lampyrinae
Within the Lampyrinae		
Ellychnia + Photinus pyralis	Monophyletic with 95% bootstrap support, but with a short branch between their shared ancestor to the next most recent common ancestor.	Ellychnia is not sister to Photinus pyralis, but diverges from Photinus macdermotti + Photinus brimleyi clade.
Photinus macdermotti 1 and 2		Flipped relative to Martin et. al
Ethra axillaris	Basal to Photinus + Pyractonema + Pyropyga	Basal to Photinus + Pyractonema + Pyropyga + Lucidota
Lucio blattinum	Sister to Lamprocera only, but with a short branch	Sister to Diaphnes + Lamprocera
Within the Photurinae		
Photuris	Basal in the Photurinae	Derived within the Photurinae
Psilocladus	Sister to Photurinae + Amydetinae	Derived Within the Luciolinae
Within the Luciolinae		
Luciola 3 + Emeia	Monophyletic, but with a short branch to the most recent common ancestor with the Pygoluciola + Luciola 4 + Curtos clade	Not monophyletic. Not sister to the Pygoluciola + Luciola 4 + Curtos clade
Asymmetricata + Luciola sp 2	Basal to Emeia + Luciola + Pygoluciola + Curtos clade	
Pollaclasis	Sister to Pterotus, but with a short branch and relatively lower support	Basal to Pterotus

The support for the named clades using the four concatenated data subsets largely matches the support from the single gene tree analyses (Figure S5). The concatenated analyses inferred trees with extremely high support (Figure S21); the posterior probabilities of the named clades were either 0.0 or 1.0. This strong support could be inflated posterior probabilities instead of true signal. The selected four MCMC replicates show identical posterior probabilities, indicating convergence of the MCMC analyses.

The most interesting results are obtained for the clade that received ambiguous support from the single gene trees: *Photinus+Ellychnia*, *Australoluciola* and Otoretinae. It is expected that we received high posterior support for *Photinus+Ellychnia* being monophyletic for the data subset with the loci support *Photinus+Ellychnia* monophyly with at least 0.95 posterior probability. Reassuringly, the other two data subsets also recovered *Photinus+Ellychnia* to be monophyletic. It is therefore most probable that *Photi-*

Figure S21: Posterior probabilities of the different clades being monophyletic for the four data subsets. The results show the posterior probabilities of the four MCMC replicates (different color shades) for the four data subsets: High posterior probability of *Photinus* being monophyletic (blue), , gene shopping (red), high sequence coverage (green) and low variance in GC content (purple). The analyses produced identical posterior probabilities for all clades except Otoretinae and Diaphanes. These posterior probabilities for all clades show extreme certainty; either full support with a posterior probability of 1.0 or full rejection with a posterior probability of 0.0.

149 *nus+Ellychnia* is indeed monophyletic. In all our analysis we recovered both *Ellychnia* itself being mono-
 150 phyletic and *Photinus* + *Ellychnia* being monophyletic, indicating that *Photinus* is paraphyletic (Figure 4).
 151 The inclusion of *Ellychnia* within *Photinus* has been reported previously (Stanger-Hall et al. 2007; Stanger-
 152 Hall and Lloyd 2015; Martin et al. 2019) and has led Zaragoza-Caballero et al. (2020) to change *Ellychnia*
 153 to *Photinus*.

154 All four data subsets agreed that *Australoluciola* is not monophyletic. In the AHE dataset from Martin
 155 et al. (2019) there are only two species belonging to *Australoluciola* (see Table S1). Our inferred results show
 156 *Australoluciola* being paraphyletic with *Pteroptyx sp* and *Trisinuata sp* nested within, agreeing with previous
 157 results by Jusoh et al. (2018). Otoretinae also consisted of only two species (*Drilaster sp* and *Stenocladus*
 158 *shirakii*) in the AHE dataset by Martin et al. (2019). Otoretinae was inferred to be monophyletic using the
 159 *Photinus+Ellychnia* 0.95 posterior probability data subset, but was not found to be monophyletic using the
 160 other four data subsets (Figure S21).

161 Finally, we present the phylogeny inferred using all 436 AHE loci using the coalescent-based approach
 162 implemented in ASTRAL (Zhang et al. 2018).

163 S14.2 Divergence times among different data subsets

Table S4: Fossils and calibration constraints for the time-calibrated divergence time analysis.

Study	Age (MA)	Data	Method
McKenna et al. (2015)	78	4 Lampyridae species, eight nuclear genes	BEAST with 15 node-calibrations
Bocak et al. (2016)	130 (120-145)	2 Lampyridae species, 13 mtDNA genes	BEAST with 2 node calibrations
Kusy et al. (2018)	80 (60-97)	8-gene dataset with 4 Lampyridae species	BEAST with 2 node-calibrations
Amaral et al. (2019)	71.9 (57.9-85.6)	13 Lampyridae species, 100 amino acid sequences	BEAST with 2 node-calibrations
McKenna et al. (2019)	90 (60-110)	2 Lampyridae species, 4,818 genes	MCMCtree with 18 node calibrations
Zhang et al. (2020)	100 (74.38-129.33)	5 Lampyridae species, 531 genes	MCMCtree with 2 node calibrations
Powell et al. (2022)	133.18 (117.86-152.47)	436 AHE loci	BEAST using node calibration with 4 fossil taxa
This study	139.85 (108.43-165.68)	37, 24 and 30 AHE loci	RevBayes using the fossilized birth-death process with 4 fossil taxa

164 Our estimated crown age is older than most previous estimates (Table S4). Toussaint et al. (2017) showed
 165 that previous divergence time estimates of McKenna et al. (2015) are likely underestimates. Specifically,
 166 McKenna et al. (2015) estimated a crown age of Elateroidea of 166.18 (151.83-181.57) while Toussaint
 167 et al. (2017) estimated a crown age of 246.02 (231.35-260.12). Most previous analyses used only very few
 168 Lampyridae species (up to five species) which could possibly bias crown age estimates if the true crown group
 169 was not sampled. Furthermore, most previous studies should not be considered as independent evidence, as
 170 for example Zhang et al. (2020) uses divergence times for calibrations which were estimated by Zhang et al.
 171 (2018).

172 Our divergences times overlap with the recent estimates by Powell et al. (2022) using the same AHE

Figure S22: Lampyridae phylogeny inferred using ASTRAL. Lampyridae phylogeny inferred from all 436 AHE loci using the coalescent-based approach implemented in ASTRAL (Zhang et al. 2018). The numbers on the nodes represent concordance factors if different from 1.0. The color coding of the tips is done according to (Martin et al. 2019).

173 dataset. The main difference in the two analysis are (i) the number of loci used (436 in [Powell et al.](#)
174 [\(2022\)](#) and up to 37 loci in this study), (ii) the chosen fossil calibrations, (iii) the fossil calibration approach
175 (node dating vs the fossilized-birth-death process), (iv) fixed topology citePowell2022 vs joint inference of
176 divergence times and topology (our study), and (v) the software BEAST vs RevBayes. It is very reassuring
177 to see the large overlap in divergence time estimates despite these differences in the performed analysis.

Figure S23: Crown age estimates of the named clades from Table S1. Each plot shows the posterior distribution of the crown age of a different clade for the four data subsets: High posterior probability of *Photinus* being monophyletic (blue), high sequence coverage (red), low variance in GC content (green) and gene shopping (purple). The estimated ages agree between the four data subsets except for the cases when the topology differed.

178 **S14.3 Sensitivity analysis of fossil calibration**

179 Our sensitivity analysis of including and excluding the recently published *Photinus* fossil, †*Photinus kazantsevi*
 180 *sevi* (Alekseev 2019), yielded largely identical results (Figure S24). †*Photinus kazantsevi* was dated to be
 181 33.9 to 37.2 million years old. Our estimated crown age of *Photinus* was between 32 and 63 Ma, including
 182 and excluding †*Photinus kazantsevi*. This result gives us confidence about our estimate of the crown age of
 183 *Photinus*.

Figure S24: Estimated crown age of *Photinus*. We show the crown age of the *Photinus* clade for the three data subsets with (top row) and without (bottom row) using the †*Photinus kazantsevi*. First, we observe that the data subset has little impact on the estimated *Photinus* crown age. Second, the usage of †*Photinus kazantsevi* does not significantly impact the *Photinus* crown age estimate, which corroborates the †*Photinus kazantsevi* placement and *Photinus* crown age.

184 S15 Convergence Assessment

185 We performed convergence assessment using the R package `convenience` (Fabreti and Höhna 2022). We
186 checked for convergence within each run, i.e., by checking that the effective sample size (ESS) was higher
187 than 625 for each continuous parameter and each split frequency (for splits that had a posterior probability
188 of $0.01 < pp < 0.99$). We checked the convergence between the four replicate runs using the Kolmogorov-
189 Smirnov test for continuous parameters and the expected difference in split frequencies. Naturally, several
190 of our MCMC analyses failed. For the MCMC analyses that failed, we proceeded as follows until we reached
191 satisfactory convergence results. First, we ran the same analyses under the same settings 4-times longer.
192 Second, we changed the weights of the moves to apply twice as many moves per iterations. Third, we ran four
193 sets of independent analyses each with their four independent replicates to find at least on set that converged.
194 This procedure was automatically performed by checking convergence automatically using `convenience` after
195 each run. An example plot is shown in Figure S25 and the detailed plot of split frequencies (Figure S26) as
196 splits frequencies were usually the most difficult parameter to reach convergence.

Figure S25: Convergence assessment using convenience (Fabreti and Höhna 2022). Here we show an example of the convergence assessment for a single locus phylogenetic analysis. This plot shows that all continuous parameters had an effective sample size (ESS) of above 625 (top left), the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic between runs of below 0.09 (top right), an ESS of splits of above 625 per split (bottom left), and a difference in split frequencies between runs lower than the maximal default threshold (bottom right).

Figure S26: Difference in split frequencies extracted from convenience (Fabreti and Höhna 2022). Here we show the difference in split frequencies between the four different replicates separately.

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